

Studies on the Complexes of 3-Hydroxy-2-Naphthaldehyde Thio Semicarbazone with Some Divalent and Trivalent Metal Ions

C. B. MAHTO

Department of Chemistry, Gopalganj College, Gopalganj

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The complexes of 3-hydroxy-2-naphthaldehyde thio semicarbazone, $C_{10}H_6(OH).CH:N.NH.CS.NH_2$, abbreviated as H_2 .ntsc with Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) of the type $M(ntsc).A$ where $A=H_2O$ and NH_3 and with Cr(III) of the type $M(ntsc).2A.Cl$ have been isolated and characterised on the basis of their elemental analyses, ir, electronic and magnetic studies. The Ni(II)-, Cu(II)- and Pd(II)-complexes are square planar, the Zn(II)-, Cd(II)- and Co(II)-complexes are tetrahedral and the Cr(III)-complex is octahedral. Only Cu(II)-, Co(II)- and Cr(III)-complexes are paramagnetic, while the Ni(II)-, Pd(II)-, Zn(II)- and Cd(II)-complexes are diamagnetic.

NUMEROUS complexes¹⁻⁹ of thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones have been reported in literature. Not merely their use in analytical processes or behaviour as pesticidal and fungicidal but also the activities of such reagents and some of their chelates against many diseases have attracted the author's attention to isolate the metal complexes with H_2 .ntsc. Moreover, there is no mention of its metal complexes, although the complexes of H_2 .stsc have been reported. H_2 .ntsc behaves like a tridentate dibasic ligand and resembles in system with H_2 .stsc. Also with a view to introduce H_2 .ntsc as a new reagent, the present investigation was undertaken and its complexes with Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Cr(III) have been studied.

Experimental

Materials: Nickel sulphate hexahydrate, copper sulphate pentahydrate, cobalt chloride hexahydrate, zinc sulphate heptahydrate, cadmium nitrate tetra-

hydrate, chromium chloride hexahydrate (all B. D. H.) and palladium chloride (A.M.) were used in the present work.

Ligand: The ligand was prepared by refluxing methanolic solutions of 3-hydroxy-2-naphthaldehyde (1.72 g) and thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (1.11 g) in presence of sodium acetate solution (0.82 g in 10 ml water) for 10 mins. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Preparation of complexes: The solutions of M(II) or M(III) (0.01 mole) in distilled water [Pd(II) in dilute HCl] and reagent (0.01 mole) in ethanol were mixed together with stirring. 2M NH_4OH solution was added gradually and the mixture digested on water bath for 30-40 mins. The complexes were filtered, washed with 30% ethanol and finally dried in air.

Results and Discussion

The colour of the complexes, pH values of their isolation, analytical data, magnetic moment values

TABLE I

Complexes	pH of formation	Colours	Analytical Data				μ_{eff} BM	Electronic spectra λ_{max}, cm^{-1}	Infrareds spectra		
			%C found (calcd.)	%N found (calcd.)	%S found (calcd.)	%M found (calcd.)			$\nu(M-O)$ cm^{-1}	$\nu(M-N)$ cm^{-1}	$\nu(M-S)$ cm^{-1}
Ni(ntsc). H_2O	8.0	Green	45.00 (45.04)	13.01 (13.13)	9.89 (10.00)	18.35 (18.36)	0.0	2480s	470m	510m	295m
Cu(ntsc). NH_3	7.5	Yellowish green	44.46 (44.50)	17.27 (17.30)	9.86 (9.86)	19.62 (19.63)	1.9	19650s	475m	505m	300m
Pd(ntsc). NH_3	5.6	Yellow	39.20 (39.24)	15.21 (15.28)	8.70 (8.73)	29.00 (29.03)	0.0	22400s	540m	495m	320m
Co(ntsc). NH_3	8.5	Brownish blue	45.00 (45.15)	17.50 (17.56)	10.00 (10.03)	18.40 (18.47)	4.8	17100s 19820	485m	505m	305m
Cr(ntsc).Cl. $2H_2O$	8.0	Green	39.25 (39.29)	11.42 (11.46)	8.70 (8.73)	14.14 (14.19)	3.8	17220 23610 37640	405m	480m	290m
Zn(ntsc). NH_3	7.5	White	44.58 (44.59)	17.20 (17.21)	9.80 (9.83)	19.99 (20.00)	0.0	—	460m	500m	295m
Cd(ntsc). NH_3	7.0	Dull Yellow	38.60 (38.66)	15.00 (15.03)	8.54 (8.59)	30.10 (30.18)	0.0	—	465m	490m	315m

(determined on Guoy's balance), absorption maxima in electronic spectra (recorded in their methanolic solutions using Hilger Unisppek Spectrophotometer) and a few selected infrared bands (recorded in KBr matrices in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} using Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer, model 621/2:2-scale change) are incorporated in Table 1. The complexes are insoluble in water. Except Cr(III)-complex, they are all soluble in methanol and carbon tetrachloride. Insolubility of the Cr(III)-complex in water and several organic solvents is probably due to its polymeric nature. Very close pH values of complex formation causes difficulties in the separation of these cations.

Magnetic moment: The Ni(II)- and Pd(II)-complexes are diamagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0$). The Cu(II)-complex ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.90$ BM) is paramagnetic and monomeric. The Zn(II)- and Cd(II)-complexes are also diamagnetic due to lack of unpaired electrons. The $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.5$ BM for the Co(II)-complex indicates the presence of three unpaired electrons and also suggests the tetrahedral structure for it. The Cr(III)-complex with magnetic moment 3.78 BM is the characteristic of six coordinate Cr(III)-complex. The moment value also shows three unpaired electrons in it.

Electronic spectra: The intense bands in 24800 and 22400 cm^{-1} regions in the spectra of the Ni(II)- and Pd(II)-complexes respectively, assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions suggest them to have the square planar structures. The band at 19650 cm^{-1} in the Cu(II)-complex may be attributed to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transition in favour of the square planar structure. Two bands one intense at 17100 cm^{-1} and the other weak at 19820 cm^{-1} in the Co(II)-complex can be assigned to the transitions from the ground state $4A_2(F)$ to the excited states $4T_1(P)$ and $4T_2(F)$ respectively in favour of the tetrahedral structure. The bands at 17220, 23610 and 37640 cm^{-1} in the Cr(III)-complex, assignable to the transitions from $4A_{2g}(F)$ to $4T_{2g}(F)$, $4T_{1g}(F)$ and $4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively and also the various electronic parameters i.e., $10 Dq = 17220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 702 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 0.68$ and $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 2.1$ are in fair agreement with the octahedral structure of the Cr(III)-complex.

Infrared spectra: The sharp band at 3440 cm^{-1} in the ligand, assignable to phenolic OH stretching frequency disappears¹⁰ in the complexes showing deprotonation by the metal ions. Moreover, $\nu(C-O)$ is also observed at 1080 cm^{-1} in the complexes.

The deformation band^{3,11} of NH of hydrazine residue i.e. amide II band at 1620 cm^{-1} in ligand shifts to lower frequencies at 1595 cm^{-1} in the complexes and modifies intensity on complex formations.

The sharp band⁹ at 1650 cm^{-1} in the ligand due to $\nu(C=N)$ of Schiff's base residue shifts to lower frequencies at $\sim 1625 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes showing the co-ordination through nitrogen atom of $-CH=N-$ (i.e. Schiff's base residue). Rao *et al*⁸ reported identical coordination. Further more, appearance of bands at 1510 cm^{-1} in all the complexes are due to $\nu(C=N)$ formed after loss of $\delta(NH_2)$ or by formation of thioenolic system $C-(SH)=NH$ at high pH. The fact is also supported by the absence of bands due to $\delta(NH_2)$ in the complexes.

The bands at 1280 and 810 cm^{-1} in free ligand are probably due to $\nu(C=S)$. Besides these bands, a weak band^{1,2} at 2510 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(SH)$ is also found in the spectrum of the ligand. This is probably due to presence of a small thioenolic form even in free ligand. However, $\nu(SH)$ band disappears in the complexes showing that M-S bond is formed due to deprotonation of SH group. Besides this, very clear bands at $\sim 1015 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(C-S)$ are observed in all the complexes. Srivastava *et al*¹³ have suggested $\nu(C-S)$ at $(1010 \pm 10) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in tripropyltin dithiocarbamate. It is also obvious that thioenolisation is more favoured during complex formation. The facts are further supported by newly formed low frequency bands. The band at 540 cm^{-1} in Pd(II)-complex may be assigned to $\nu(Pd-O)$. Other $\nu(M-O)$ bands appear at 485-10 cm^{-1} . Similarly, $\nu(M-N)$ have been observed at 510-480 cm^{-1} . Such assignments for $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ have also been supported by earlier workers¹⁴. The bands at still lower frequencies i.e., at 320-295 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu(M-S)$. In case of the complexes of bidentate ligands, higher frequencies for M-S may be expected^{5,9}. The band at 280 cm^{-1} in the Cr(III)-complex is probably due to $\nu(Cr-Cl)$. The bands at 830-1580 and 3370 cm^{-1} in the Ni(II)- and Cr(III)-complexes only show the presence of coordinated water molecules.

On the basis of these evidences, the following tentative structures of the complexes have been proposed:

where, M = Ni(II), Pd(II), Cu(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II).

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